

Living Labs Implementation Manual

LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

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1. Introduction

European consumers are showing an **increasing interest in alternative food protein products** as a substitution towards the conventional animal-based foods [1]. Consumers growing pull towards such products is an **excellent opportunity to enhance efforts toward healthier and more sustainable diets**, in line with the ambitious targets of the European Green Deal [2], as well as the Farm to Fork Strategy [3].

Despite such an increasing interest, **animal-based foods still capture the majority share in our diets**, accounting for about 67% of our protein intake. For example, 94% of Europeans still consume animal-based products on a daily basis [4]. The **reasons are manifold**. As animal and alternative protein-based diets are two interconnected food consumption behaviours, their relationship favouring the former can go back to the general desire of people to consume conventional animal-based products or to other factors that are correlated directly to the latter. Research so far supports that people at points **lack information or knowledge** about the benefits (environmental, nutritional, health) of consuming alternative protein foods as a direct substitute of animal-based ones [5]; have **negative perception of the sensory properties** of alternative protein foods, together with limited **familiarity** with such products [6]; perceive alternative protein products as **not so easily accessible** (lack of choice, availability as well as convenience) [7] and as relatively **more expensive** than their counterparts [8]. When it comes to availability and choice, **the risk of potential allergens in such products** and/or the **need for a balanced nutritional profile** becomes a consumption barrier for some consumers [6]. The **lack of a clean label, as well as guidance** on safety requirements for novel, alternative protein-based foods can also act as a barrier, especially for those consumers for whom health and safety are the determining factors of their food consumption habits [9].

Looking at food environments more closely, people perceive the **promotion and marketing efforts as limiting and/or isolating** which can then act as a barrier towards their increased consumption. For example, in most cases alternative protein products are promoted using **segregated language** such as ‘vegan’ or ‘vegetarian’, as opposed to other (animal) product / dishes where the nutritional or other sensory properties are highlighted [10]. This is especially true for consumers who might be curious but still consider themselves as carnivores. Another example is the **placement of alternative protein products** in isolated supermarket shelves or separate menu pages, a tactic that deprives these products from even the chance of being considered as possible options by consumers. Such isolation or segregation practices are followed at other points of sale (e.g., restaurants, food markets, canteens) as well [9]. Additionally, **prevalent social and cultural norms** make animal-based products to take precedence, while the consumption of alternative proteins being potentially discouraged or downplayed [10]. To cap off the exemplification of factors that disfavour the consumption of alternative protein foods are **vendor related ones** where the **availability and accessibility** to alternative food protein sources and products **becomes more difficult due to supply volatility such as shortages, gluts or failures** [11].

The above well-known barriers can at the same time act as leverage points towards the facilitation and scaling up of the consumption of alternative proteins. As an evolving field, **more research is needed** to understand consumer perceptions and how consumption of alternative protein products can be promoted. **Further research and development** should also go in the direction of alternative protein sources and the introduction of novel products and as a means to offset some of the above-identified barriers at the value / supply chain level.

1.1 LIKE-A-PRO – alternative proteins, consumers and food actor engagement

Inspired by and capitalising on these developments, the LIKE-A-PRO project aims to **accelerate the shift towards and normalise healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns** by **diversifying and increasing** the **availability, accessibility** and **uptake** of alternative sources of protein and specific products.

Sixteen new alternative protein products will be developed during the course of the project, based on ingredients from **seven protein sources** which are novel, sustainable, EU-based, healthy, affordable and industry viable. In addition to these products, LIKE-A-PRO will **co-design and promote other types of solutions**, such as governance mechanisms which hold the potential to promote alternative protein supply and products in food environments, including their promotion and uptake at the consumer level. Examples of these include policies that look at reducing the portfolio of unsustainable products, marketing strategies, guidelines for human-centric campaigns and similar.

Accordingly, four **inter-linked and iterative clusters of activities** will support reaching out the project goals:

- **Food environments and consumers:** in this cluster, the focus is placed on better understanding consumer behaviour-related determinants, consumers' food choices and the necessary food environment (contextual) frameworks that enable a higher uptake of alternative protein products.
- **Alternative protein product diversification and development:** in this cluster, the goal is to diversify the alternative protein supply and develop new alternative protein products, thereby increasing the availability and accessibility of such products in the European markets. Best product value propositions will be developed based on consumer, market and regulatory considerations.
- **Mobilising food system actors:** in this cluster, the project will work with key food system actors to support them in utilising the project learnings and empower them to make alternative protein products an easy and economically viable choice via their diversified & increased market supply and favourable food environment conditions.
- **Impact and regulatory assessment:** in this cluster, the aim is to ensure that the project will bring about positive changes in terms of health and sustainability of the European food system. Socio-economic, health, and environmental impact assessments as well as alignment with regulatory and ethical considerations are central to this clusters.

The food environments and consumers (cluster 1) and, to a lesser degree, the development of alternative protein products (cluster 2), are the clusters that will interact with the consumer engagement activities through living labs, subject of this report.

1.2 What is this Manual about?

The **LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Manual** provides a comprehensive overview of the **key activities and steps** to consider when **planning and implementing** the LIKE-A-PRO living labs and their iterations. It closely follows the overarching guidance laid out in the **Governance Framework**. For each lab iteration and interaction point, the Manual includes **suggested agendas, facilitation techniques**, and **templates for reporting and transcription**. In addition, a range of **supporting materials** is provided.

Together, these resources contribute to a **coherent and systematic planning and implementation process** across all participating countries, while also supporting **consistent data reporting and comparability**.

The **primary audience** for this Manual is the **local lab implementers** operating in the **11 European countries** involved in the LIKE-A-PRO project. However, the Manual's **open and adaptable language** also makes it relevant for **anyone interested in setting up and running living labs** beyond the project's context.

The Manual is complemented by the following key resources:

1. **The LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Governance Framework [12]**. This outlines the essential procedural considerations for the successful planning, establishment, operation, and monitoring of the living labs. It defines and integrates key elements such as the labs' vision, purpose, focus themes, target groups, locations and timelines, operational procedures, and team roles and responsibilities.

2. **The Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES) [13]**. This strategy supports lab implementers in maximizing citizen participation. It offers guidance on recruitment approaches and methods for sustaining participants' interest throughout the lab process.
3. **Train-the-Trainer Workshops [14]** – Three workshops were organized to ensure that all local lab implementers share a common understanding of the labs' structure and goals, and to equip them with the skills needed to successfully deliver the labs.

2. The LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

2.1 The mandate and purpose of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs

The LIKE-A-PRO living labs will act as a **forum to exchange, discuss and co-create** with European citizens / consumers on a range of topics related to their food choices and the way these are made in different food environments. The specific focus and context, following the project mandate, will be the consumption and integration of alternative protein products into European diets. More specifically, through the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, the project team will:

1. **Explore food environments** from the **perspective of European citizens and their consumption realities** (how consumers make their choices in such environments how easy it is, what are the challenges / opportunities and similar);
2. **Test and receive** some **feedback on the newly developed alternative protein products** also, naturally, only where possible and while complying with all regulatory and ethical requirements in a high standard manner.
3. **Uncover and study** the most **influential consumer behavioural determinants**, the leveraging of which has the potential to drive the shift towards healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns; and
4. **Explore and promote entry points in food environments** in the form of governance mechanisms or solutions, the introduction of which can create favourable conditions in such environments to facilitate the much-needed dietary shift.

Following such a mandate, the more specific themes of focus as well as the desired results are detailed in **Section** Error! Reference source not found.. and Error! Reference source not found.. of the Living Labs Governance Framework report.

2.2 The guiding principles of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs

Connecting Research to Real Life. Living Labs aim to connect research to real-world settings, departing from the often ideal but artificial conditions of lab experiments. These real-life contexts are crucial for the development of services, products, and innovations, as they provide insights for addressing particular challenges right from the start. Additionally, in the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, consumers are engaged in various real food environments, such as supermarkets, restaurants, university canteens, and food markets, facilitating interaction and research.

Diverse Techniques for Innovation. While adapting to real-world contexts, living labs employ a multi-method approach as the various topics that are in focus direct information sharing and collaboration with lab participants. Accordingly, in LIKE-A-PRO living labs various interactive facilitation methods will be used in an iterative process to analyze consumer habits, generate ideas, co-create solutions, and understand their needs and motivations regarding alternative proteins. The specific methods will be selected during the planning and meetings of each lab iteration.

Empowerment and Collaboration. A third principle deduced from the argumentation above is that participants should not merely be passive subjects of study but be actively engaged as collaborative contributors to comprehend real-world contexts and create innovations for them. Thus, participants are regarded as experts in their field who can give recommendations and guidance, fostering a sense of ownership and self-efficacy at the same time. The latter sets the living labs approach apart from other citizen engagement formats. This third principle is taken into account especially when formulating strategies to encourage the uptake of alternative proteins into consumers' dietary choices.

Inclusivity. To create value that addresses the diverse needs and desires of all stakeholders within the given context is the primary goal of living labs. To achieve this, LIKE-A-PRO living labs tap into the diverse expertise of domain experts, even though their primary target group remains citizens. Hence, stakeholders of real food environments are taken into account to observe real-life behaviors. Importantly, the insights of these stakeholders - as well as of others like policymakers, civil society organizations, and research - will be considered in refining solutions co-created with citizens. This ensures that multiple perspectives are integrated into transparent, credible, and implementable solutions.

Added value and sustainability. The fifth principle extends from involving diverse stakeholders and creating value that serves both citizens and key stakeholders in the present and the future, aiming to outline paths for a better quality of life within environmental constraints. This understanding of sustainability is achieved by fostering continuous learning and converting the knowledge from the living labs into models, methods, and practical implications. This approach encompasses economic, ecological, and social aspects.

The principles have been developed on basis of the various similar living labs handbooks and methodology outlines [15-18].

3. Implementing the Living Labs

3.1 Lab iteration 1 (choice editing) guideline

3.1.1 Introduction

This section serves as a **guideline for the design and implementation** of the LIKE A PRO living labs **lab Iteration 1** that focuses on **choice editing**. It contains two types of interaction points with consumers: 1). **Conventional exchanges** and 2). **Interaction at the point of sale**¹.

The guideline contains **suggestions for an agenda, interaction flows, methods** to conduct the interactions with the consumers. In addition, the **list of materials** needed during as well as before and after the meeting are included in this document.

Lab implementers are **welcome to implement the guideline as it is outlined here**, and/or **tailor and adapt it** according to learnings from **previous experiences with consumer engagement processes**. Nonetheless, there are key points each lab implements would need to follow: 1). The aims / goals of each interaction point; 2). The type of interaction point; 3). Participant KPI as well as considerations for a diverse and inclusive sample; and 4). Reporting back the results utilising the templates that have been included as part of this guideline. In case some

¹ For a more detailed overview of terms such as lab iteration, choice editing and/or types of interaction points, please have a look at the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs' Governance Framework.

of these key points are not met, a lab implementer might be asked to repeat the exercise to ensure coherence and consistency in the implementation of the process across all 11 European LIKEA-A-PRO living labs.

Pro tip: the LIKEA-A-PRO Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy provides a detailed outline hints and tips (successful factors) that can increase the chances for an increased curiosity from consumers and reaching a diverse and inclusive participant sample.

Pro tip: lab implementers are advised to consider and follow the Covid-19 developments in their own countries and consider its consequences on the implementation of the labs. This might require a switch from in-person to online living labs.

Figure 1: Timeline of the LIKEA-A-PRO Living Labs Iteration 1 (focused on choice editing)

3.1.2 Interaction Point 1. Living lab type: conventional exchanges

3.1.2.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

Main lab iteration goals

1. Introduce, inform and make aware European citizens / consumers (i.e., lab participants) about the LIKEA-A-PRO project as well as Living Labs, including here their goals, activities and desired impact;
2. Set up the context and inform participants about the different possibilities for collaboration and engagement throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond in other project activities;
3. Exchange and get a first feeling about Europeans' attitudes, preferences as well as readiness to integrate alternative proteins in their dietary patterns;
4. Jointly reflect with European consumers on their feelings, opinions as well as justification degree (for social and environmental gains) of choice editing as one approach towards the promotion of alternative proteins and reduction of animal-based products;
5. Co-create with lab participants the modalities to promote choice editing mechanisms by different stakeholders and frame the respective boundaries in view of the current stages of socio-economic development;
6. Enable and promote interaction, networking as well as social cohesion among people with different backgrounds.

3.1.2.2 Suggested agenda flow

Timing	Agenda item
30' (before the meeting)	Registration
Setting the scene	
10'	Welcome, agenda and objectives of the workshop
15'	The LIKE A PRO project and living labs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the project about, including the alternative proteins that we will be producing? (touching upon health and environmental benefits, including social and economic) • What are the living labs and what does the participant journey looks like (opportunities for engagement) • QA
10'	Getting to know each other and energising activity
How ready are we for alternative proteins? – a quick exercise	
30'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercise • Joint reflection about our capabilities, motivations and opportunities to integrate alternative proteins into our dietary patterns
Choice editing: a joint reflection on advantages and disadvantages of such cluster of mechanisms	
10'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An introduction to 'choice editing' and what would it mean in practice
40'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of the next exercise / joint working groups • Joint group work / exercise • Reporting back and another pulse check
A roadmap towards effective and consumer prioritising choice editing solutions: menu of options for stakeholders: the do's and don'ts	
30'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An introduction to the joint exercise • Joint group work / exercise
Closing and next steps	
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick feedback round
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closing and next steps

*Please reserve some time for coffee breaks as well as lunch and/or other similar arrangements depending when the meeting will take place.

3.1.2.3 Suggested techniques and flows for some of the group work sessions

Session 1: How ready are we for alternative proteins? – a quick exercise

Main facilitation method(s): COM-B [19]; group work in plenary.

Suggested flow:

- 5' | Moderator explains the participants the joint group work (as seen below). Moderator provides a brief overview of what is the COM-B and how it is utilised.
- 25' | Plenary group work: moderator guides participants as well as facilitates the joint reflection about people's readiness to integrate alternative proteins in our diets. Approx. 8 min are spent on each COM-B categories, namely, Capabilities, Motivations and Opportunities. A dedicated note-taker takes stock of people's input. This could be live and showcases on a beamer, so participants can better understand others' contributions. A note-taking template will be provided as part of the guideline. The purpose is not to be detailed, but to get a general feeling what participants are thinking about alternative proteins as a whole.

- **Guiding question:** if you would think about the integration of alternative proteins in your dietary patterns, what are some of the key enabling or hindering factors you could think of? Let's use the COM-B model to guide our thinking here:

COM-B category	Prompt for participants	Complementing question for moderators in case participants are not reacting directly
Capability	Psychological skills: knowledge, information, memory, attention, cognitive abilities	How much are you aware (knowledge, information) about alternative proteins and the possibility of relying on them as a source of protein and accordingly integrating them into your diets?
	Physical: bodily skills, abilities or disabilities	Are there any physical limitations that you could think of that could affect you in embedding such proteins into your diet?
Motivation	Reflective: thought planning process, involving assessment of outcomes and intentions	What are some of the key motivators (health, financial, habits, fear, curiosity, adventure) that could impact your willingness to consume more alternative protein-based products?
	Automatic: emotional reactions, desires, impulses, habits etc.	
Opportunity	Physical: time, financial resources, location, availability, accessibility	What are some of the external factors (beyond yourself as an individual) that you think can impact the decision to integrate alternative proteins in your diet? Think of time, financial resources, location, availability, accessibility, opinions of your peers etc.
	Social: cultural norms, opinions and behaviours of social peers and those surrounding us	

Session 2: Choice editing: a joint reflection on advantages and disadvantages of such cluster of mechanisms

Main facilitation method: World Café.

Suggested flow:

- 5' | Moderator provides an introduction to 'choice editing' as a concept and what would it mean in practice.
- 5' | The introduction is followed by a quick QA and also a showcase of quick opinions in a popcorn format (*the latter means that participants share their thoughts quite quickly and without much deliberation – the moderator moves from one participant to the other*).
- 40' | Moderator explains how the group work will look like and proceeds to divide people in groups.
- The facilitation method is World Café. Participants will discuss each question in rotating rounds. There will be 3 tables each hosting one of the questions. Participants will move from one table to the other and discuss the respective question with the moderator. Participants will spend about 12' on each table. The guiding questions for each table are as follow:
 - **Table 1:** How would you react to certain limitations in product assortment? Do you think the removal of certain products would be helpful for consuming more sustainably and healthy?
 - **Table 2:** Would you justify such an approach as a means to ensuring that sustainability and health agenda is advanced on the EU level?
 - **Table 3:** What are the opportunities and/or barriers stemming from such a way forward – i.e., choice editing approaches

Session 3: A roadmap towards effective and consumer prioritising choice editing solutions: menu of options for stakeholders: the do's and don'ts

Main facilitation method(s): developed by the project team; group work: break-out groups

Suggested flow:

- 5' | Moderator explains the purpose of this exercise which is more hypothetical in the sense that if we take 'choice editing' as granted, how would we aim to achieve the implementation of such mechanisms and what are the key points key decision makers (policy and industry, as the most influential actors) would need to consider from consumers' perspectives.
- 25' | Group work. Moderator guides participants through the discussion and the element of the group work: do's and don'ts (presented in a 2-column table) and the key decision makers: policy and industry. The moderator would entice people to think about the key discussion topics while considering the key decision makers and their potential actions. For each point that participants would bring forward, ideally would connect it to a decision maker (by means of a sticky dot / icon).
 - What are the points you would be fine with and you think would not intervene with our perceived autonomy as we know it?
 - Where would you draw the limit and thinks certain degrees are not acceptable?

3.1.2.4 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of the interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- An introductory slide deck: LIKE-A-PRO project, living labs and respective details, including overall journey.
- A definition of what we mean by alternative sources of proteins and products and the ones we are considering in the project as well as guiding our living labs exchanges. This could be presented in a slide but then also a poster, which can act as a prompt during the exchanges with consumers.
- Slide deck which outlines: 1). the COM-B model (with its 3 main categories) in a nutshell; 2). a more detailed overview of its categories; 3). the guiding questions of the session 3 exercise vis a vis the COM-B model.
- A one-page document outlining the COM-B model which can be laid down throughout the tables where the living lab participants are sitting.
- A slide deck on choice editing, its definition and what it would mean in practice, including a rationale to why such measures might be important to talk and consider.
- A mock version of the World Café facilitation material, which can then be replicated in a large brown sheet paper (session 2).
- A mock version of the do's and don'ts facilitation material, which can then be replicated in a large brown sheet paper (session 3).
- A slide on the next steps pertaining to the living labs methodology and opportunities for engagement.
- A short survey which can be shared with the lab participants to learn more about their experience with the LIKE-A-PRO living lab interaction point (e.g., what went well, what could be improved and similar) from their perspective as a participant.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.1.3 Interaction Point 2. Living lab type: point of sale

3.1.3.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

1. Inform and make aware European citizens / consumers (i.e., lab participants) about the LIKE-A- PRO project as well as Living Labs, including here their goals, activities and desired impact;
2. Inform participants about the different possibilities for collaboration and engagement throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond in other project activities;
3. Exchange and get a first feeling about Europeans' attitudes, preferences as well as readiness to integrate alternative proteins in their dietary patterns;
4. Jointly reflect with European consumers on their feelings, opinions as well as justification degree (for social and environmental gains) of choice editing as one approach towards the promotion of alternative proteins and reduction of animal-based products

3.1.3.2 Key points

- This interaction point with consumers (i.e., at the point of sale) has to a large degree the same aims as the previous interaction point, with the only difference is the format of engagement. The conventional exchange is more artificial in a way that people can prepare themselves mentally on what potentially might come and polish their thoughts and opinions, leading to more polished insights too. An interaction at the point of sale may capture the natural event as it unfolds in field settings (not artificial), where subjects feel more familiar with and provide impromptu insights. This allows for more spontaneous insight collection which are less polished and thought through, increasing their credibility.
- It is important to highlight, this living lab type even though is implemented in a food environment i.e., point of sale where consumers make their choices and purchase products, does not aim to intervene or change something in the food environment itself. This is mainly because of limitations in resources, but also because in the project we have envisioned to undertake 4-behavioural intervention pilots (another project activity) which will be undertaken by changing the food environment settings. Accordingly, for such a living lab type, we have we have opted for an approach that allows for the engagement of consumers at a point of sale (natural habitat) in a resource efficient manner, while avoiding overlaps with other project activities.

3.1.3.3 Key organisational points

- For conducting this living lab type, lab implementers are would need to establish a partnership with a food environment / point of sale where the activities would be implemented. For the purpose of reaching a diverse and inclusive sample, it is recommended these food environments to be conventional ones and not fall under the categories of organic and/or food environments that are oriented towards offering sustainable products and services. Ideally, a collaboration and permission with respective representatives is sought in advance.
- Similarly, for diversity and inclusivity, it is recommended to repeat the exercise in more than one location / neighbourhood where people from different socio-economic backgrounds live.
- For the effective implementation of this living lab type and the suggested activities one might need more than one moderator. 2 moderators is the recommended minimum, but more could be encouraged for reaching or talking to more people at the same time, including a successful capture of the exchange.

- In addition, a longer presence might be required (e.g., 5-8 hours) since only in this way one could reach to more people, but also diverse sample e.g., if we take a supermarket, it is well-known that elderly people do their groceries earlier in the day, employed people later on and similar.
- For capturing people’s creativity, it is a good idea to make a creative and visible stand e.g., with the project branding, banners and similar.

3.1.3.4 Flow suggestions

- Moderator starts the conversation by greeting and explaining to the participant the context of the exercise, including here a brief overview of the project and living labs. Since one will not be able to deliver a full presentation, ideally the information provided is in a snapshot and people would be invited to check out the website and/or get in touch for more information. For this purpose, having some information materials at hand is a good idea: flyers, leaflets, business cards, QR codes for the website etc.
- To kick off the content exchange, one could start the conversation by asking the person what they have bought (or in case the purchase hasn’t happen yet, what they will be buying), their general grocery list and habits. One could also have a look at their purchase bill and/or grocery bags for a more playful conversation; in case the person is fine with this – in case the conversation happens after the person has made their purchases. This is just a warm up exercise, hence, please feel free to improvise and choose a manner that you think it would work best in the context of the food environment the exercise is being undertaken.
- Moderator then would proceed to ask the person about some of the more living lab related questions. The questions would be more or less the same as with the previous interaction point, but in a short and combined manner. Please see a suggestion of the potential questions in the table below.
- The format in here could be of different nature (as seen below – sub-bullet points). However, what is important is that the technique would lead to qualitative input (elaborated thoughts by people) to allow for consistency (i.e., it’s not preferred one partner to do a more quantitative survey and others rely on qualitative approaches). Lab implementers could also adopt other techniques that would equally lead to the desired outcomes / results (as outlined above).
 - Format 1 (and preferred): it is recommended that this is a free-floating conversation where the moderator asks the questions and the person responds. To capture the exchange, the conversation is either recorded (upon the agreement of the person) or a second moderator (project member) takes notes;
 - Format 2: at the point of sale, the person is introduced to the context and is invited to participate and share their opinion via a digital survey either on the spot and/or at home. However, the survey questions should be designed in such a way that the questions will lead to elaborated responses;
- At the end, participants are asked for their demographic characteristics and the consent for their information to be utilised in the project.

3.1.3.5 Guiding questions

1. Consumer attitudes towards alternative proteins. What do you think about alternative proteins and respective products? Would you be open to integrate them in your dietary patterns. Moderator could rely on the below table (in a similar fashion) as in the interaction point 1.

COM-B category	Prompt for participants	Complementing question for moderators in case participants are not reacting directly
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Capability	Psychological skills: knowledge, information, memory, attention, cognitive abilities	How much are you are aware (knowledge, information) about alternative proteins and the possibility of relying on them as a source of protein and accordingly integrating them into your diets?
	Physical: bodily skills, abilities or disabilities	Are there any physical limitations that you could think of that could affect you in embedding such proteins into your diet?
Motivation	Reflective: thought planning process, involving assessment of outcomes and intentions	What are some of the key motivators (health, financial, habits, fear, curiosity, adventure) that could impact your willingness to consume more alternative protein-based products?
	Automatic: emotional reactions, desires, impulses, habits etc.	
Opportunity	Physical: time, financial recourses, location, availability, accessibility	What are some of the external factors (beyond yourself as an individual) that you think can impact the decision to integrate alternative proteins in your diet? Think of time, financial recourses, location, availability, accessibility, opinions of your peers etc.
	Social: cultural norms, opinions and behaviours of social peers and those surrounding us	

2. Choice editing. **How would you react if at the (insert point of sale) the purchase of animal-based products / specific product in case one has been identified by the grocery link / bags / purchase would have been made more difficult e.g., through price increases or reduced availability / accessibility?** The below listed prompts could ensure the continuity of the conversation and generation of insights.

- Justify such approaches because they promote better health
- Justify such approaches because they promote pro-environmental practices
- Quite neutral
- Concerned
- Other

3.1.3.6 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of the interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- Short communication materials on the project and living labs such as flyers, leaflets, one-page descriptions.
- Business cards and/or QR codes for more information – *developed by the respective lab implementers.*
- A definition of what we mean by alternative sources of proteins and products and the ones we are considering in the project as well as guiding our living labs exchanges. This could be presented in a slide but then also a poster, which can act as a prompt during the exchanges with consumers.
- A small poster on the COM-B model Couple of slides which outline: 1). the COM-B model (with its 3 main categories) in a nutshell; 2). a more detailed overview of its categories; 3). the guiding questions of the first guiding question. Similar fashion as in the interaction point 1.
- A slide deck on choice editing, its definition and what it would mean in practice, including a rationale to why such measures might be important to talk and consider – it can be printed in an A4 paper sheet.
- A short survey which can be shared with the lab participants to learn more about their experience with the LIKE-A-PRO living lab interaction point (e.g., what went well, what could be improved and similar) from their perspective as a participant.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.2 Lab iteration 2 (choice expansion) guideline

3.2.1 Introduction

This document provides guidelines for the second iteration of the LIKE A PRO Living Labs, focusing on choice expansion. Unlike the previous one, this iteration will centre on a single type of interaction point / lab type: workshops or conventional exchanges. It is recommended **to conduct 2 to 3 rounds**, with each workshop involving **10 to 15 participants**. The **exact number of rounds will depend** on the **specific KPIs each lab implementer must meet**.

Workshops are preferred due to the need for in-depth interaction, as outlined below. While venues like restaurants or canteens could be considered to implement the workshop, **implementing the suggested flow in the context of lab type point of sale could be challenging**. This is because the number of questions and the time required, over 15 minutes, to generate meaningful insights may not be feasible in these environments.

Specifically, the section of the manual provides suggestions for an agenda, interaction flows, and methods to engage consumers. It also includes a list of materials needed before, during, and after the sessions.

Lab implementers are encouraged to follow this guideline as outlined or adapt it based on learnings from previous consumer engagement experiences. However, there are key points that each lab implementer must adhere to:

1. The goals of each interaction point.
2. The type of interaction point to be used.
3. Participant KPIs and ensure a diverse and inclusive sample.
4. Use provided templates for reporting results.

Failure to meet these key points may require a repeat of the exercise to maintain coherence and consistency across all 11 European LIKEA-A-PRO Living Labs implementations.

Pro tip: The LIKE-A-PRO Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy outlines hints and successful factors that can increase consumer curiosity and help achieve a diverse and inclusive participant sample.

Pro tip: Lab implementers are advised to monitor and respond to Covid-19 developments in their respective countries, as these may necessitate a switch from in-person to online living labs.

3.2.2 Aims / goals and outcomes

Main lab iteration goals

1. **Engage** with **European consumers** to comprehensively **understand their opinions, beliefs and preferences** regarding **alternative protein products**. This includes capturing diverse perspectives across different demographic groups to identify trends, barriers, and motivators related to alternative protein consumption.

2. **Utilise the insights** gathered to determine the most compelling product propositions and the necessary **marketing efforts / strategies** to effectively promote alternative protein products, ensuring alignment with consumer expectations and preferences to drive adoption and market success.

Complementary lab iteration and overall living labs goals

3. **Introduce, inform, and raise awareness** among European citizens/consumers (reminding returning participants) **about the LIKE-A-PRO project and Living Labs**, including their goals, activities, and intended impact.
4. **Provide context and inform participants** about the various **opportunities for collaboration and engagement** throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond, including other project activities (reminding returning participants).
5. **Facilitate and encourage interaction, networking,** and **social cohesion** among people from diverse backgrounds.

3.2.3 Suggested agenda flow

Timing	Agenda item
30' (before the meeting)	Registration
Setting the scene	
10' <i>(the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).</i>	Welcome, agenda and objectives of the workshop Icebreaker activity: activity to make participants comfortable and encourage interaction
20' <i>(the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).</i>	The LIKE A PRO project and living labs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the project about, including the alternative proteins that we will be producing? – include aspects of health, sustainability, and market trends. • What are the living labs and what does the participant journey looks like (opportunities for engagement) • QA – to ensure participants have a good understanding
Session 1: (Food, alternative protein) Tasting, evaluation and exchange	
70'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercise • Food tasting, evaluation and exchange
Session 2: Joint reflection	
15'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group discussion to enable participants to share their overall thoughts and impressions.
Closing and next steps	
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick feedback round
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closing and next steps

*Please note, due to the revised workshop structure lunch is included as part of the overall exercises. Coffee break could be included in-between session 1 and 2.

3.2.4 Suggested flows for this interaction

Session 1: Food tasting, evaluation and exchange

Main facilitation method: Gallery Walk:

- **3 product stations** per round of workshops showcasing:
 - a). uncooked products ready to be tried / eaten (e.g., snacks, cheese, ham (appetizer like), dips etc.) as well as in their packaged form;
 - b). a cooked meal / dish as well as the packaged form of the alternative protein ingredient; and
 - c). a dessert, including their packaged form and/or the packaged form of the main alternative protein ingredient.

The **samples should be smaller in size** to ensure that each **participant has their own portion** and to **help prevent saturation challenges**.

- Participants walk around the different stations and try out the products and provide feedback to the questions. **For this session 70'** has been allocated, hence, **approx. 23'** can be spent per **product station**.
- Please find the **overview of stations and respective questions** and **supporting materials** in the following Miro board: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKjF_vkw=?share_link_id=561259854537
- Please find below **a recommended build-up of stations** and **some facilitation tips**.
- The questions are similar from one station to the other, but this is expected due to the nature of the exercise. We can use this to our advantage to juxtapose participant (group) responses and see if similarities or trade-offs are present from one station to the other.

Type of products:

- The original intent of this lab iteration was to gather feedback from European consumers on alternative protein products, dishes, and meals that contain or are based on alternative protein sources considered in the project. However, following consultations with partners, it appears that **some of these novel alternative protein sources are not yet available on the market**. Please refer to the first table below for an availability overview. Please refer to second table below on a short guidance on how to select the products for the various stations.

Availability of alternative protein sources in the living labs target countries (based on partner's expertise)

Country	Rapeseed Kernel	Mealworm	Krill	Microbial	Cultivated Mushroom	Fermented Fungal	Pea
Denmark	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Finland	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Germany	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Greece	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Italy	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Norway	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Poland	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Slovenia	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spain	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

The Netherlands	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Turkey	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes

Guidance on selecting products

Choosing alternative protein products for the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs lab iteration 2	Are the project AP sources and products available in the lab country?	Yes (all or some)	Please select the products by considering the following suggestions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on the overview table, in case your country has the possibility to work with some of the more novel sources of alternative proteins, please consider doing that. This is for the purpose of having the possibility to generate insights for all alternative protein sources considered in the project.
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the workshops you could 1). decide to work with the same source of protein e.g. mushroom protein for all 3 stations or 2). choose products with different sources of protein (e.g., station 1 mushroom; station 2: krill; station 3: pea Following, if the first option is chosen, then please in the next workshop round focus on other alternative protein sources.
		No	Are any other alternative protein sources available in your country?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If yes, please feel free to consider those. If not, which is highly unlikely, please reach out to the lab coordinator to discuss other ways forward.

Important:

- Participants will be asked about **any food allergies** they might have. Dishes will be prepared **using non-allergenic ingredients whenever possible**. To avoid biased results, **dishes will ideally not be overly 'polished.'**
- Due to **differences in availability**, achieving **consistency in the alternative proteins used across countries is challenging**. Therefore, we will not aim to use the same sources in every country. Partners are free to choose products based on availability and the suggestions provided. When **analysing and documenting results**, we will **clearly explain how the process was conducted**.
- Due to **organizational difficulties**, **recipes** for the suggested dishes/meals **will not be provided**. The preparation will be at the discretion of the lab implementers.
- The reporting and transcription templates will be designed to collect all relevant information for documentation and result analysis.

Recommended Build-Up of the Stations

- **Product Display Table:** Each station should have a table showcasing the product in both its packaged form and ready-to-eat form. The packaged form should be available in multiple samples so participants can examine it in detail if needed. The ready-to-eat form should also be available in sufficient quantity for participants to try, although smaller sample sizes are recommended to avoid saturation.
- **Information sheet for the cooked meals / dishes and desserts:** Include brief information sheets or cards for these products detailing key ingredients, nutritional information, and any unique features. This helps participants understand what they are tasting and provides context for their feedback.
- **Feedback Cards:** Provide cards for participants to fill out with their feedback on the respective questions related to the products. Mock cards have been provided for the questions requiring such form of feedback collection.
- **Large Pinboard:** Set up a large pinboard displaying the remaining questions. Participants can add their responses to this board using sticky notes or by writing directly on it.

Tips for Facilitation

- **Encourage Interaction:** Emphasize that this is a workshop rather than a conventional product tasting exercise. While individual feedback is important, participants should be encouraged to engage in discussions, elaborate on their answers verbally, and interact with one another and the facilitators throughout the session. *This is an important element for the purpose of differentiating our approach from other more conventional product tasting approaches.*
- **Promote Elaborate Feedback:** Facilitators should actively encourage participants to provide detailed and thorough feedback. Prompt them to explore their opinions more deeply and ensure that all observations and comments are captured.
- **Facilitator Engagement:** Ensure that facilitators are approachable and actively involved. They should circulate among the stations (if not specific facilitator per station is available), engage with participants, answer questions, and facilitate discussions to make the session more dynamic and insightful.
- **Provide Guidance:** Offer guidance on how participants can structure their feedback and discussions. This can help them articulate their thoughts more clearly and contribute more effectively to the overall evaluation.
- **Manage Time Effectively:** Keep track of time to ensure that participants have adequate opportunities to engage at each station while also moving through the workshop efficiently.

Session 2: Joint reflection

Main facilitation method: Plenary session

Flow: The facilitator gathers all participants in a plenary session and asks them to share their overall impressions and thoughts, including what stood out to them. This exercise facilitates discussions about different stations and products, encouraging participants to compare and contrast their experiences and insights. One facilitator takes notes during this session.

Guiding questions:

- What are your overall impressions of the products you've tried today?
- Did discussing with others change or reinforce your initial thoughts about the products?
- What are the key takeaways from today's workshop?
- How has your perception of alternative proteins changed after participating in this workshop?

3.2.5 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of the interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- An introductory slide deck: LIKE-A-PRO project, living labs and respective details, including overall journey.
- A map of the Gallery Walk and product station composition as well as questions and respective sheets / templates (*provided in the Miro board above*).
- A slide on the next steps pertaining to the living labs methodology and opportunities for engagement.
- Reporting and transcription template.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.3 Lab iteration 3 (choice environment) guideline

3.3.1 Introduction

This section provides **guidelines for the third iteration of the LIKE A PRO Living Labs**, focusing on **choice environment**. It contains two types of interaction points with consumers: 1). Conventional exchanges and 2). Interaction at the point of sale².

Specifically, the document provides suggestions for an agenda, interaction flows, and methods to engage consumers. It also includes a list of materials needed before, during, and after the sessions.

Lab implementers are encouraged to follow this guideline as outlined or adapt it based on learnings from previous consumer engagement experiences. However, there are key points that each lab implementer must adhere to:

1. The goals of each interaction point.
2. The type of interaction points to be used.
3. Participant KPIs and ensure a diverse and inclusive sample.
4. Use provided templates for reporting results.

Failure to meet these key points may require a repeat of the exercise to maintain coherence and consistency across all 11 European LIKEA-A-PRO Living Labs implementations.

Pro tip: The LIKE-A-PRO Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy outlines hints and successful factors that can increase consumer curiosity and help achieve a diverse and inclusive participant sample.

Pro tip: Lab implementers are advised to monitor and address potential health risks in their respective countries, as these may require a transition from in-person to online living labs.

² For a more detailed overview of terms such as lab iteration, choice editing and/or types of interaction points, please have a look at the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs' Governance Framework.

Interaction points

Partners are encouraged to select from the interaction points listed below. Each option is designed to ensure consistent outcomes, regardless of the chosen route.

- **Route 1 (preferred):** One workshop and one interaction at a point of sale.
- **Route 2:** Two workshops (the second as a substitute for interaction at the point of sale). Partners may choose to focus each workshop on specific topics, such as: Workshop 1: Food Environments; Workshop 2: Labels.
- **Route 3:** Two workshops (same as in route 2) and one interaction at a point of sale.

3.3.2 Interaction Point 1. Living lab type: conventional exchange

3.3.2.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

Main lab iteration goals

1. **Explore the Impact of Food Environments' Design on Consumer Behaviours:** Understand how elements such as product placement, product prominence, and overall environmental design influence consumer behaviour and purchasing patterns, particularly regarding alternative proteins and sustainable, healthier consumption.
2. **Investigate the Role of Behavioural Science Tools in Shaping Consumer Choices:** Engage with consumers to explore how behavioural science tools—such as nudging, defaults, priming, and other techniques—can influence their purchasing decisions and encourage the adoption of alternative proteins.
3. **Understand Consumer Perception of and Use of Labels:** Gain insights into how consumers perceive and navigate food labels, particularly in the context of alternative proteins, and identify which labelling strategies would be most effective in helping consumers make informed decisions amidst the diverse range of labels currently on the market. *The outcome of this exchange will contribute directly to the main product of this lab iteration: the 'Best Label Format Proposition from a Consumer Perspective.'* The latter provides added value for lab participants and could serve as a key highlight or primary hook in recruitment and communication materials.

Complementary lab iteration and overall living labs goals

4. **Introduce, inform, and raise awareness** among European citizens/consumers (reminding returning participants) **about the LIKE-A-PRO project and Living Labs**, including their goals, activities, and intended impact.
5. **Provide context and inform participants** about the various **opportunities for collaboration and engagement** throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond, including other project activities (reminding returning participants).
6. **Facilitate and encourage interaction, networking, and social cohesion** among people from diverse backgrounds.

3.3.2.2 Suggested agenda flow

Timing	Agenda item
30' (before the meeting)	Registration
Setting the scene	
	Welcome, agenda and objectives of the workshop

5' (the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).	Icebreaker activity: activity to make participants comfortable and encourage interaction
10' (the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).	The LIKE A PRO project and living labs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the project about, including the alternative proteins that we will be producing? – include aspects of health, sustainability, and market trends. • What are the living labs and what does the participant journey look like (opportunities for engagement) • Q&A – to ensure participants have a good understanding
Session 1: The Influence of Food Environments on the Purchase and Consumption of Alternative Proteins	
60'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercise • Activity: Exploration of food environments
Session 2: Co-creating the future of European food labels for alternative proteins	
45'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercises • Activity: Label Perception and Usage in the Context of Alternative Proteins
Feedback and closing	
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick feedback round and closing

*Please reserve some time for coffee breaks as well as lunch and/or other similar arrangements depending when the meeting will take place.

3.3.2.3 Suggested flows for this interaction

Session 1: The Influence of Food Environments on the Purchase and Consumption of Alternative Proteins

Main facilitation method: Food Environment Walkthrough

Participants will explore three distinct food environment stations, each featuring a mix of alternative protein products/dishes and conventional animal-based proteins.

Stations Overview:

Station 1: Supermarket Display: Compare segregated shelving (alternative proteins separated from conventional proteins) with integrated shelving (both product types displayed together).

For this station, both the integrated and segregated mock-ups (facilitation materials) will be used.

- On the integrated mock-up, please remove the green colour from the tags.
- The goal is not to replicate a full supermarket experience, and time is limited. Therefore, the mock-ups can be positioned closely together.
- Participants will view both the integrated and segregated mock-ups (alternative and conventional) and select 1–3 products. They may choose from either or both displays. However, product choices are not the focus of the discussion. The questions will remain more general.
- Please note the group composition guide included below in the session flow.
- Questions and flow are outlined below.

Station 2: Restaurant Setup: Explore segregated and integrated strategies applied in restaurant menus.

For this station, both the integrated and separated menus (facilitation material) will be displayed.

- The goal is not to replicate a full restaurant experience, and time is limited. Therefore, the mock-ups can be placed close together.

- Participants will view both the integrated and segregated mock-ups (alternative and conventional) and select 1–3 dishes. They may choose from either or both menus. However, the selected dishes are not the focus of the discussion, as the questions will remain more general.
- Please note the group composition guide included below in the session flow.
- Questions and flow are outlined below.

Station 3: Experimenting with Defaults, Priming, and Pricing: Review images (facilitation material) of integrated shelving designed to test how defaults (e.g., making alternative proteins the default option), priming (subtle cues encouraging specific choices), and pricing strategies influence consumer decisions.

- For the supermarket shelves, please use the integrated version with green-coloured price tags. The products include visuals, images, and wording, so facilitators should keep these elements in mind when guiding and conversing with participants. No further adjustments are needed.
- For the menu, please use the highlighted integrated version with cues. Adjustments have already been made.
- Please note the group composition guide included below in the session flow.
- Questions and flow are outlined below.

Participant Instructions:

1. Visit each station and observe the setup and the images displayed.
2. Choose one or more products you would purchase and note them down on a piece of paper.
3. After making your selections, converse with the facilitator(s) and your group participants on some questions / topics.

Facilitator instructions:

1. Divide participants into small groups to encourage active discussion and engagement. Aim for balanced group sizes to ensure everyone has a chance to contribute.
2. Display the provided questions prominently next to each mock-up or station. This will serve as a visual prompt to guide participants' discussions and keep them focused on the key topics.
3. Allow each group enough time to thoroughly engage with the materials and discuss the questions at each station. This is a group exchange, besides the small amount of time for self-reflection as seen in the 'participant instructions'
4. The overall minimum time for this session is 60 minutes. However, the overall time required will vary depending on the number of interactions points you've selected (refer to the first page for details). Adjust the schedule accordingly to ensure meaningful exchanges.
5. Prompt groups to share their thoughts openly and consider different perspectives. Remind them to reflect on both personal experiences and general impressions when answering the questions.

Station-Specific Follow-Up Questions:

Station 1 (Conventional Supermarkets):

- Which shelving style (segregated or integrated) made it easier for you to find and select alternative proteins? Why?
- How did seeing alternative proteins next to conventional products make you feel about trying or buying them? Did they become more trustworthy or appealing?
- Did the layout make it easier for you to compare alternative proteins with conventional options? Why or why not?
- What did the placement of alternative proteins suggest to you about their 1) quality, 2) importance, or 3) how 'normal' they are compared to conventional products?

Station 2 (Restaurant Menu):

- Did the segregation or integration of dishes spark your curiosity to try alternative proteins? Why?
- Which setup (segregated or integrated) felt more intuitive and convenient when selecting a meal quickly?
- How did the presentation affect your view of alternative proteins as a satisfying and legitimate meal choice?
- If this setup were used in your local restaurant, would it influence your regular choice of alternative proteins? How?

Station 3 (Defaults, Priming, Pricing):

- If alternative proteins were the default option on the menu, how would that influence your choice? Would you stick with the default or switch to conventional options? Why?"
- What specific visual or messaging cues (e.g., images, colours, wording) influenced your decision to choose or avoid alternative proteins?"
- How did pricing or discounts affect your willingness to select alternative proteins?"
- What emotional or practical factors positively influenced your choice of alternative proteins (e.g., curiosity, confidence, convenience)?"
- Did you experience any hesitation or doubts that made you less likely to choose alternative proteins? How could these concerns be addressed?"

Session 2: Co-creating the future of European food labels for alternative proteins

Main facilitation method: Label Walkthrough

Participants will be presented with a variety of product labels, each highlighting different types of information: detailed nutritional profiles, simplified labels with key points, labels emphasizing sustainability or ethical sourcing. The labels that we will focus on are presented in the table below. Most of the labels are present in each of the implementing countries, besides two Nutri Score and the Planet Score. The latter albeit their limited availability, are interesting to find out if and how they are perceived by consumers in various European countries / regions.

Label name	Short description	NO	DK	ES	DE	SI	TR	GR	FI	IT	NL	PL
EU Organic (Euro Leaf)	Official organic certification across Europe.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Demeter (Biodynamic Farming)	Certification for biodynamic farming, stricter than EU organic.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Fairtrade	Ensures ethical sourcing and fair labour conditions.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rainforest Alliance	Focuses on sustainable farming and biodiversity.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Marine Stewardship Council (MSC)	Certification for sustainable seafood.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Nutri-Score	Nutrition label grading food from A (healthiest) to E (least healthy).			X	X						X	
Planet Score	Evaluates the environmental impact of a product in the categories of pesticides,											

	biodiversity, climate and animal welfare											
V-Label (Vegetarian)	Recognized certification for vegetarian products.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
V-Label (Vegan)	Recognized certification for vegan products.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Vegan Trademark (The Vegan Society)	Official vegan certification from The Vegan Society.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Participant Instructions:

1. Carefully examine each label and vote the top 3 labels which would convince you to buy products containing alternative proteins.
2. Reflect on your choice and prepare to share your thoughts during the discussion.
3. Complete the short survey that the facilitator will provide. After filling it out, engage in a discussion with both the facilitator and the other participants to exchange thoughts and insights.

Facilitator Instructions

1. Invite participants to freely walk around and examine all the labels at their own pace. Encourage them to take note of any labels that stand out.
2. After the initial exploration, ask participants to fill out the provided sheets individually. Please prepare this survey sheet based on the input below. This allows them to reflect on their choices without external influence.
3. Divide participants into balanced groups to ensure diverse perspectives in each discussion.
4. At each discussion station, provide prompts related to the labels to guide the conversation and keep participants focused.
5. Encourage participants to share their thoughts openly, reflecting on both their individual choices and the group’s perspectives.
6. Ensure everyone has a chance to contribute, and guide the conversation as needed to maintain engagement.

Individual survey

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or find the following aspects important when making food choices. **In your responses, please consider your choices related to conventional products versus alternative proteins.** Use the scale below:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
 - 2 = Disagree
 - 3 = Neutral
 - 4 = Agree
 - 5 = Strongly Agree
- A. I am aware that labels are designed to guide my behaviours.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - B. I trust labels.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - C. I can understand the kind of information provided on labels.
[1][2][3][4][5]

- D. I use labels to find environmental information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- E. I use labels to find social information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- F. I use labels to find economic information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- G. I find the number of labels on a product reasonable.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- H. The format of the label (how it looks like) is important to understanding the information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- I. The actor behind the label (or the label provider) is important to me.
[1][2][3][4][5]

Discussion

Open-Ended Feedback:

- Begin by sharing your general impressions of the labels.
- What stood out to you, either positively or negatively, as you reviewed them? Why did you select those 3 specific labels?

Focused Questions:

- **Ease and Appeal:**
 - Which label did you find easiest or most inviting? Why?
- **Desired Characteristics:**
 - What are the key characteristics or types of information you value in a label?
 - Is there anything missing from the labels that you would like to see on products, both conventional ones and those on basis of alternative proteins?
- **Trust and Credibility:**
 - Which label did you trust the most? What made it feel credible?
- **Impact on Purchasing Intentions:**
 - How does the simplicity or complexity of a label affect your likelihood of purchasing the product?
 - Do you feel simpler labels with clear, concise information would make it easier to choose a product?
- **Preferred Information:**
 - How much detail should a label provide?
 - What other type of information (e.g., health benefits, sustainability claims) do you find most helpful on products containing alternative proteins?

3.3.2.4 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- An introductory slide deck: LIKE-A-PRO project, living labs and respective details, including overall journey.
- Images, banners showcasing the various stations to act as facilitative materials for session 1.
- An overview of different labels (in an image or banner format) to act as facilitative material for session 2.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.3.3 Interaction Point 2. Living lab type: point of sale

3.3.3.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

This interaction point aligns with the same aims, goals, and outcomes as the previous interaction point.

Setup

Please engage with consumers at different points of sale after they have made their food choices. You can use their shopping basket, selected products, meals, or dishes as a starting point for the conversation (depending on the point of sale). For motivation, living lab partners could offer to participants some alternative protein-based products, meals or dishes.

Participants can fill out the survey questions sheet on their own or with assistance, depending on their preference. However, it's important to collect and note the responses. Please clarify with the participants in case they have any questions regarding specific terms such as green claims etc.

Please develop enough survey questions sheet that can be handed to the participants based on the input below.

Discussion

General reflection questions

1. How did you decide which products, meals, or dishes to pick? Could you walk us through your thought process?
2. Did you pick an option with alternative proteins? Why (not)?
3. When shopping / making your choice, did you feel guided in making certain decisions or not? If so, by what?

Survey questions (food environments)

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or find the following aspects important when making food choices. In your responses, please consider your choices related to conventional products versus alternative proteins. Use the scale below:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

- A. The way the offerings are arranged is important to me.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- B. I value the ease of finding products, meals, or dishes.
[1][2][3][4][5]

- C. Labels influence my purchasing decisions.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- D. Green claims (e.g., sustainability or environmental benefits) are significant to me.
[1][2][3][4][5]
- E. Images and the visual appeal of products, meals, or dishes impact my choices.
[1][2][3][4][5]

Survey Questions (Labels)

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or find the following aspects important when making food choices. In your responses, please consider your choices related to conventional products versus alternative proteins. Use the scale below:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
 - 2 = Disagree
 - 3 = Neutral
 - 4 = Agree
 - 5 = Strongly Agree
- A. I am aware that labels are designed to guide my behaviours.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - B. I trust labels.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - C. I can understand the kind of information provided on labels.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - D. I use labels to find environmental information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - E. I use labels to find social information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - F. I use labels to find economic information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - G. I find the number of labels on a product reasonable.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - H. The format of the label (how it looks like) is important to understanding the information.
[1][2][3][4][5]
 - I. The actor behind the label (or the label provider) is important to me.
[1][2][3][4][5]

3.3.3.2 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- Templates for question 1 and 2 (*to be adapted by partners based on the above content*).
- Reporting and transcription templates.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.4 Lab iteration 4 (beyond choice) guideline

3.4.1 Introduction

This section provides **guidelines for the fourth iteration of the LIKE A PRO Living Labs**, focusing on **beyond choice**. It contains two types of interaction points with consumers: 1). Conventional exchanges and 2). Interaction at the point of sale³.

Specifically, the document provides suggestions for an agenda, interaction flows, and methods to engage consumers. It also includes a list of materials needed before, during, and after the sessions.

Lab implementers are encouraged to follow this guideline as outlined or adapt it based on learnings from previous consumer engagement experiences. However, there are key points that each lab implementer must adhere to:

1. The goals of each interaction point.
2. The type of interaction points to be used.
3. Participant KPIs and ensure a diverse and inclusive sample.
4. Use provided templates for reporting results.

Failure to meet these key points may require a repeat of the exercise to maintain coherence and consistency across all 11 European LIKEA-A-PRO Living Labs implementations.

Pro tip: The LIKE-A-PRO Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy outlines hints and successful factors that can increase consumer curiosity and help achieve a diverse and inclusive participant sample.

Pro tip: All exchanges with participants should be documented, depending on the session design. According to the guidelines, the **following options apply**: 1). participants can write down their thoughts; 2). both participants and facilitators can document the exchanges (recommendable in case participants don't write down their contributions); or 3). participants can respond via an online poll, survey, or a physical sheet.

3.4.2 Interaction Point 1. Living lab type: conventional exchange

3.4.2.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

Main lab iteration goals

1. **Explore how communication framing, language, and message design** can be leveraged to promote sustainable and healthy consumption, particularly alternative proteins, through messaging that is engaging, relatable, and impactful across diverse audiences.
2. **Examine the influence of cognitive biases such as social norms, emotions, simplification** on behaviours, and discover how to effectively engage leverage such insights to drive positive shifts toward healthier, more sustainable lifestyles.
3. **Identify key touchpoints for food literacy and sustainability education**, with an emphasis on alternative proteins, across different life stages, from early childhood to adulthood, and reflect on how lifelong learning can support lasting dietary and cultural transformation.

³ For a more detailed overview of terms such as lab iteration, choice editing and/or types of interaction points, please have a look at the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs' Governance Framework.

Complementary lab iteration and overall living labs goals

4. **Introduce, inform, and raise awareness** among European citizens/consumers (reminding returning participants) **about the LIKE-A-PRO project and Living Labs**, including their goals, activities, and intended impact.
5. **Provide context and inform participants** about the various **opportunities for collaboration and engagement** throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond, including other project activities (reminding returning participants).
6. **Facilitate and encourage interaction, networking, and social cohesion** among people from diverse backgrounds.

3.4.2.2 Suggested agenda flow

Timing (total, excl. registration 190 min)	Agenda item
30' (before the meeting)	Registration
Setting the scene	
5' (the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).	Welcome, agenda and objectives of the workshop Icebreaker activity: activity to make participants comfortable and encourage interaction
10' (the timing for this session is indicative. Please feel free to adjust it according to what you think it would work best).	The LIKE A PRO project and living labs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the project about, including the alternative proteins that we will be producing? – include aspects of health, sustainability, and market trends. • What are the living labs and what does the participant journey look like (opportunities for engagement) • Q&A – to ensure participants have a good understanding
Session 1: Language and Messaging that Moves	
85'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercise • Activity: Engagement stations on utilisation of behavioural science for more effective communication and impactful consumer-oriented narratives.
Session 2: Education Touchpoints: From Childhood to Higher Age	
85'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and explanation of the joint exercises • Activity: education for healthier and sustainable eating patterns across the lifespan
Feedback and closing	
5'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick feedback round and closing

*Please reserve some time for coffee breaks as well as lunch and/or other similar arrangements depending when the meeting will take place.

*Please feel free to decide if you want to break this workshop into two mini workshops focused on each session and/or reduce the interaction time if you feel is needed. However, it's important for the questions to be tackled as described.

Highlight: All content sessions outlined under Interaction Point 1 of this guideline are mandatory. However, partners are welcome to deliver these sessions as a single workshop or divide them into two or more workshops, depending on their preferred format and audience needs.

3.4.2.3 Suggested flows for this interaction

Session 1: Engagement Stations – Language and Messaging that Moves

Session Flow

Step 1: Warm-Up Exercise (10')

Instructions

- Participants reflect individually on a memorable campaign, advertisement, or communication initiative, ideally within the food sector and/or food context. Examples from other sectors are also acceptable. Please note, this is just a warm up exercise.
- Facilitator Prompt: Think of a campaign, ad or communication initiative (ideally within the food sector and/or food context) that left a lasting impact on you. What made it memorable?
 - Please see points on a list of initiatives and examples below.
- Participants briefly share reflections in plenary.

Step 2: Engagement Stations (1-hour)

Set up: 3 stations, 20 minutes each, participants are divided into groups and stay in those groups throughout the entire exercise (step 2).

- Each station will feature an overview of initiatives that have incorporated or have been built on basis of cognitive biases, otherwise known behavioural science principles.
 - **Station 1:** Incentives & Reinforcements: encouraging behaviours through rewards and consequences
 - **Station 2:** Nudging & Choice Architecture: making the desired behaviour easier and more likely without too much burden
 - **Station 1:** Social Influences & Norms: leveraging social dynamics
 - **Station 3:** Feedback & Information Provision: providing actionable insights
 - **Station 2:** Framing & Messaging: influencing decisions through message design
 - **Station 3:** Goal Setting & Habit Formation: encouraging long-term behaviour change
 - **Station 3:** Emotional Appeals & Psychological Triggers: harnessing emotions to drive behaviours

A slide deck elaborating further on the above-mentioned behavioural science principles is provided. Similarly, examples of messaging / initiatives that are built on such principles (these are not real-world examples) are provided. Lab implementers are encouraged to utilise those and tailor / adapt the language to match the local context. These examples can be presented using posters or slide decks for clarity and engagement.

Instructions

- Participants review all examples individually.
- Participants, individually, on an exercise sheet, rate each on a scale of 1–5 for:
 - Clarity of message | 1 (very unclear) – 2 (somewhat unclear) – 3 (neutral) – 4 (clear) – 5 (very clear)
 - Likelihood to influence behaviours- in general (does not need to be the participant's behaviour) | 1 (very unlikely) – 2 (unlikely) – 3 (neutral) – 4 (likely) – 5 (very likely)
- Participants continue with deeper group reflection and exchanges:
 - Which types of messages were more appealing or resonated more deeply? Why?
 - Did you notice a pattern in what made messages more effective?
 - Which initiative stood out to you the most, and why? Please pick your top 2.
 - Can you think of campaigns that successfully shape or shift public thinking about alternative proteins over time?

Step 3: Plenary Reflection and closing of this session (15')

Instructions

Set up: plenary, online poll, followed by a general reflection

- In your opinion, are more effective initiatives (e.g., campaigns, ads, or other communication efforts) those that make a strong, one-time impact, or those that build a story and evolve over time? | 1 (strongly prefer one-time impact) – 2 (somewhat prefer one-time impact) – 3 (no strong preference) – 4 (somewhat prefer evolving narrative) – 5 (strongly prefer evolving narrative).
 - To help guide participants' thinking for this exercise, examples from previous activities could be used (one illustrating a long-term initiative and another showcasing a short-term initiative).
- Participants explain their reasoning.
- Group reflects on implications for an initiative's strategy and messaging longevity.

Session 2: Sustainable Education Touchpoints: From Childhood to Higher Age

Session Flow

Participants are divided into small groups. If possible, groups are mixed by age to foster intergenerational insights and contrasting experiences.

Step 1: Reflective Time Exercise (40')

Instructions

- As a prompt participants discuss the below listed questions for about 10 minutes:
 - Think back over your life: what were the key moments when you learned something about food, nutrition, or how we consume? Who taught you, and in what setting?
 - Was there a moment when food education (both with regard to sustainability and health) felt especially relevant to your life circumstances?
- Participants move to the second part of the exercise: reflecting and discussing in their groups on:
 - Formal education (classes and curricula across different educational levels, school, university and/or similar, equivalent institutions' canteens)
 - Informal education (family, culture, extracurriculars)
 - Other (public canteens, posters, health campaigns, life milestones)
- Participants place food educational milestones (using colour coded sticky notes, markers etc. reflecting the three categories above) on a shared timeline spanning 1955 to 2025.
- After placing general food education milestones on the timeline, participants repeat the process: this time focusing specifically on sustainability and alternative proteins (it's recommended that this is done in another colour to distinguish from the previous bullet). Guiding Questions:
 - When did you first encounter ideas about sustainability in your diet, whether or not the term 'sustainable diet' was used?
 - Did anyone: teachers, family, media, ever talk to you about eating less meat, trying new proteins, or thinking about the environment? If so, how did it make you feel?
 - What kind of messages did your school, university or an equivalent institution send, implicitly or explicitly, about what kinds of food are 'normal' or 'good'?
- Continuing the group discussion: impact assessment. Guiding questions:
 - How did these experiences influence your current eating habits or perceptions of food sustainability?
 - Were there any missed opportunities that could have shaped your thinking earlier?
 - What messages stuck with you and why?

Step 2: Future Visioning Exercise (45')

Instructions

- Scenario Setup: Imagine it's 2035. Sustainable diets and alternative proteins are now deeply embedded in European education systems, from kindergartens to universities, and even lifelong learning programs.
- Groups brainstorm what this future looks like. One can sketch, bullet, or storyboard their ideas. Guiding Prompts:
 - What makes learning about food and sustainability exciting and relevant for a 6-year-old? A 16-year-old? A 60-year-old?
 - What are students of different ages learning about alternative proteins (e.g., plant-based, fermented, cultured meats) and why?
 - What new knowledge, tools, or attitudes do teachers have to confidently teach about alternative proteins and food sustainability?
 - How did teacher training programs evolve to prepare educators for this topic?
 - How did school, university and/or other equivalent institutions' canteens become living classrooms for learning about alternative proteins and sustainable diets?
 - What education policy changes were implemented to prioritize sustainable diets and alternative proteins in school systems?
- Group Sharing and closing the session. Each group shares one or two key ideas from their future vision. Facilitator draws connections, identifies recurring themes, and ends with a reflection:
 - How might your idea have changed your own experience growing up?
 - What's one thing we can advocate for now to shift the future of food education?

3.4.2.4 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of interaction point

- Participant list and consent form.
- An introductory slide deck: LIKE-A-PRO project, living labs and respective details, including overall journey.
- A short explanation of the session 1 behavioural science principles in the form of a slide deck.
- A list of example initiatives that have been built on basis of behavioural science principles (Session 1).
- Mock-up banner featuring a timeline of learning journeys for both past reflections and future visioning (Session 2).
- Reporting and transcription templates.

Please note that some additional facilitation materials need to be prepared directly by the lab implementers e.g., facilitation papers outlining key questions and sheets for the individual rating exercises.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we're happy to share more details upon request.

3.4.3 Interaction Point 2. Living lab type: point of sale

3.4.3.1 Aims / goals and outcomes

This interaction point aligns with the same aims, goals, and outcomes as the previous interaction point.

Set up

Please engage with consumers at different points of sale after they have made their food choices. You can use their shopping basket, selected products, meals, or dishes as a starting point for the conversation (depending on the point of sale). For motivation, living lab partners could offer to participants some alternative protein-based products, meals or dishes.

Below are two suggested exchange ideas for engaging participants. **Lab implementers may choose to explore either idea based on the flow of interaction.** It's **not necessary to explore both ideas with the same person**, however, **ideally, both ideas should be explored equally**, e.g., if interacting with 20 participants, aim to discuss each idea with approximately 10 participants.

Exchange idea 1: Language and Messaging that Moves

Instructions

- **Warm up** / Open exchange with the person: “Think back to a campaign, advertisement or communication initiative (ideally within the food sector and/or food context) that really stuck with you. What was it about the message, or how it was delivered, that made it memorable? – Facilitator takes notes.
- You'll now review four campaign-style taglines promoting alternative proteins. Each one highlights a different focus style. For each message:
 - Rate it from 1 to 5 on:
 - Did it make you want to act, or feel something? | 1 (not at all) – 2 (slightly) – 3 (moderately) – 4 (quite a bit) – 5 (very much / strong emotional pull).
 - How much does this speak to your own values, tastes, or identity? One scale for all / general impressions | 1 (not at all) – 2 (slightly – doesn't really align with me) – 3 (neutral) – 4 (fairly well – I see myself in this message) – 5 (strongly – this reflects me and my values).
 - Briefly explain your rating.
 - Note the one thing that stood out most to you: this could be a word, tone, feeling, or imagery the message evoked. Questions to help reflection:
 - What type of person do you think this message is speaking to?
 - What would you change to make this message more powerful or relatable?

Campaign Taglines: Alternative Proteins. Please note: the explanations (expl.) below are more for the benefit of the lab implementers and not so much about the participants – only if they ask.

- Eat smart. Feel better. One plant-based bite at a time.
 - Expl. **Harnessing emotions to drive behaviours** (feeling better is an emotional reward); **Encouraging long-term behaviour change** (promotes gradual, sustainable steps); **Making the desired behaviour easier** (small steps, “one bite at a time”)
- Millions have already made the switch. Join the movement for a planet-friendly plate.
 - Expl. **Leveraging social dynamics** (social proof: millions already switched); **Encouraging behaviours through rewards** (belonging to a movement feels rewarding).
- Juicy. Satisfying. Surprisingly plant-based.

- Expl. **Influencing decisions through message design** (breaking expectations with “surprisingly,” creating curiosity); **Harnessing emotions** (triggering desire with “juicy” and “satisfying”); **Making behaviour easier/more likely** (reducing perceived sacrifice: it’s satisfying).
- The food of tomorrow is already here. What does your plate say about you?
 - Exp. **Influencing decisions through message design** (framing it as futuristic and aspirational); **Harnessing emotions** (identity and pride — what your plate “says” about you); **Encouraging long-term behaviour change** (implies being ahead of the curve, sustainable future)
- Plants: The protein source you didn’t know your grandma would love.
 - Expl. **Harnessing emotions** (nostalgia and warmth: referencing grandma); **Leveraging social dynamics** (if even grandma loves it, it’s socially acceptable and desirable); **Making the behaviour easier** (reduces perceived risk: if grandma likes it, it must be good!).

Exchange Idea 2: Sustainable Education Touchpoints

Instructions

Opening Prompt: When did you first start learning about what should be on your plate? Do you still follow what you learned back then or did your dietary patterns changed through time?

- Quick Poll Questions:
 - Were you ever taught about plant-based or alternative proteins in school, university and/or other equivalent institutions? | 1 (never) – 2 (rarely – mentioned briefly or in passing) – 3 (occasionally – included in some lessons / sessions but not emphasized) – 4 (frequently – covered in multiple lessons / sessions or discussions) – 5 (extensively – it was a core or well-integrated topic)
 - Did your school, university and/or other equivalent institutions canteen reflect what you were being taught about nutrition or sustainability? | 1 (Not at all – there was a clear disconnect) – 2 (Slightly – some overlap, but not consistent) – 3 (Moderately – mixed signals; some reflection of what was taught) – 4 (Mostly – the canteen generally aligned with educational content) – 5 (Completely – strong, visible alignment between teaching and food options)
 - Did food education in school influence your current food choices or beliefs? | 1 (Not at all – it had no impact on my current choices or beliefs) – 2 (Slightly – I was aware of it but it didn’t stick) – 3 (Moderately – it influenced me to some extent) – 4 (Significantly – it shaped some of my habits or views) – 5 (Very strongly – it plays a major role in how I eat or think about food today)
 - How well do you think schools today are preparing students for sustainable food futures? | 1 (Not at all – schools are failing to address this issue) – 2 (Poorly – minimal or outdated efforts) – 3 (Adequately – some coverage, but room for improvement) – 4 (Well – clear efforts and integration into education) – 5 (Extremely well – sustainability is a core part of food education today)
- Future-Facing Prompt (Visioning for 2035): It’s 2035, and you’re back in school. Which of these food education experiences would have made the biggest impact on you, and why?
 - Choose one or more, or create your own!
 - Adding “Food and Climate” as a core subject, covering sustainable eating, alternative proteins, and global food systems.
 - Integrating hands-on growing projects (like mushrooms, beans or cultured meat) into science and biology classes.
 - Weekly cafeteria challenges tied to lessons on nutrition, sustainability, and food innovation.
 - Making environmental impact labels (carbon, water, land use) part of cafeteria menus, with students calculating and reflecting on choices in math or geography classes.

- Creating interdisciplinary projects where students design their own sustainable food startups.
- Adding practical “Future Food Skills” classes, teaching students how to cook with alternative protein products.

3.4.3.2 An overview of the materials that will be prepared and are needed for the delivery of interaction point

- Participant consent form.
- Mock-up banners to outline the different campaign taglines (exchange 1).
- Reporting and transcription templates.

Please note that some additional facilitation materials need to be prepared directly by the lab implementers e.g., facilitation papers outlining key questions and sheets for the individual rating exercises.

To respect space limitations, confidentiality, and the internal nature of certain processes, the facilitation materials referenced in this report have not been included. However, if practitioners are interested, we’re happy to share more details upon request.

4. Conclusion

The LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Manual is a flexible and practical guide created to inspire and support meaningful engagement with consumers around alternative proteins. It’s built on real-life experiences and participatory values, offering a structure that helps plan and run living labs in a way that fits local contexts while staying connected to the overall goals of the project.

Instead of prescribing rigid steps or one-size-fits-all solutions, the Manual shares a clear and useful set of agendas, methods, and facilitation tools. These are designed to help implementers create open, inclusive spaces, whether in supermarkets, canteens, or community workshops, where people can share ideas, ask questions, and co-create solutions around food choices and environments. From behavioural frameworks like COM-B to interactive formats like gallery walks and world cafés, the Manual encourages creative ways of working that lead to rich, grounded insights.

The Manual isn’t about making everything the same. On the contrary, it welcomes flexibility and adaptation. Implementers are encouraged to shape the tools and approaches to match their local social, cultural, and institutional settings. Built-in reflection and iteration points also support learning and improvement along the way.

While it’s made for LIKE-A-PRO labs, the Manual can also be a helpful resource for other practitioners working in food system change. Its methods, themes, and overall approach can be adapted and used elsewhere, helping build a wider picture by comparing insights across different places and groups.

At its core, the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Manual supports a collaborative and exploratory process. It sees consumers not just as research participants, but as partners in imagining what healthier, more sustainable, and more appealing food choices can look like in everyday life.

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